

Completing the census of low-mass stars and brown dwarfs towards the Chamaeleon clouds

Karolina Kubiak,¹ Koraljka Mužić,¹ Ines Sousa,¹ Victor Almandros-Abad,¹ Rainer Köhler, Alexander Scholz²

¹ CENTRA, Faculdade de Ciências, Universidade de Lisboa, Portugal

² SUPA, School of Physics & Astronomy, University of St Andrews, UK

Abstract

The molecular cloud complex of Chamaeleon hosts one of the richest populations of young low-mass stars in the Solar vicinity. However, the stellar and substellar census of several young clusters and groups towards this region is still incomplete. This is starting to change thanks to the availability of wide-field missions such as Gaia, allowing for robust candidate selection using photometry, proper motions and parallaxes. In this contribution, we present the optical spectroscopic follow-up of low-mass stars in Cha I and ϵ Cha selected from Gaia DR2 and 2MASS. Our work identifies several new members of Cha-I, and increases the census of spectroscopically confirmed ϵ Cha members by more than 40%. We derive the first IMF in ϵ Cha that extends into the substellar regime (down to $\sim 0.03 M_{\odot}$), and we find it to be consistent with that of other young clusters. We point out similarities between ϵ Cha and the southernmost part of Lower Centaurus Crux, both lying at similar distances and sharing the same proper motions. This suggest that the two groups may have been born during the same star formation event.

1 Introduction

The Chamaeleon complex is a set of dark clouds located at a distance of ~ 200 pc, and a place of intense star formation activity. Other young populations such as ϵ Chamaeleonitis and the southern part of Lower Centaurus Crux (LCC) are found nearby on the sky, but at shorter distances (~ 100 pc). While the centers of these young populations have been thoroughly studied, the census is still highly incomplete in the periphery of the main star formation sites. Thanks to the availability of wide-field photometric and astrometric surveys, we can now efficiently look for young stars and brown dwarfs over large extended regions of the sky, and thus help improve our understanding of the star and brown dwarf formation processes in low-density environments.

2 Selection of the new candidates

To examine such a large region as shown in Fig. 1, we first plotted stellar surface density maps. Each map was limited to the distances of known members for Cha I, Cha II and ϵ Cha (obtained from *Gaia*). The final step of the selection of the new candidates is based on their expected red colors, and clustering in both proper motion and parallax space, using the data from *Gaia* DR2 and 2MASS. We identify in total 35 new candidates (see Fig. 2).

3 Follow-up spectroscopy

To confirm the membership of our candidates, we followed-up 18 objects with the FLOYDS spectrograph mounted at a 2-m robotic telescope at Siding Springs Observatory, Australia. The optical spectra allow us to determine the spectral types and extinction, and reveal the objects' youth through $H\alpha$ emission and the shape of the gravity sensitive lines of Na I.

Figure 1: The region covered in our study, along with the candidates associated with Cha I and Cha II star forming regions (~ 200 pc), and ϵ Cha moving group and/or the southern part of the Lower-Centaurus Crux association (LCC; ~ 100 pc).

The spectral template fit was performed using the spectra of field dwarfs (see Fig. 3), as well as those belonging to young star forming regions (age 1 – 3 Myr), and the TW Hydra (TWA) moving group (age 8 – 10 Myr).

Figure 2: An example of the member selection procedure for the region encompassing ϵ Cha and the southern part of the LCC.

Figure 3: One of the candidate spectra, along with the best fitting template from each class. The gravity-sensitive Na I doublet is marked, as well as the $H\alpha$ emission.

4 Ages and mass distribution

Most of the spectroscopic candidates are confirmed as young members of Cha I, ϵ Cha, and/or LCC. Moreover, the positions in the Hertzsprung-Russell (HR) diagram (Fig. 4) speak in favor of most of the other candidates also being young ($\sim 1 - 10$ Myr).

We derive the first Initial Mass Function (IMF) in ϵ Cha extending into the substellar regime (Fig. 5). The IMF can be represented by two power laws with a break around $0.5 M_{\odot}$. For $M < 0.5 M_{\odot}$, $\alpha = 0.42 \pm 0.11$ and for $M > 0.5 M_{\odot}$, $\alpha = 1.44 \pm 0.12$. Both values are in agreement with the power-law slope of low-mass IMF in various star-forming regions. This IMF estimation is only illustrative since the membership of ϵ Cha is still not complete, especially in the substellar regime.

Figure 4: HR diagram for all the candidates, along with the BT-Settl isochrones (solid lines, *Allard et al. 2011*) and the lines of constant mass (dotted lines). The isochrones correspond to the ages (1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 10, 20, 30) Myr, from top to bottom. The masses are in M_{\odot} .

5 Conclusions

This contribution is only a summary of the project. A detailed description will soon be published in A&A (*Kubiak et al., 2021*).

We obtained low-resolution optical spectra for 18 of our candidates, 4 in Cha I, and 14 in ϵ Cha. We confirmed the young evolutionary stage of 16 candidates.

We confirmed 13 new members spectroscopically and rely on X-ray emission as youth indicator for 2 more in ϵ Cha. These 15 new members increase the census of ϵ Cha by 43%. Our spectral fits and the location in the HR diagram show that the new members of the ϵ Cha moving group have a similar age as the TW Hydrae association (8 – 10 Myr; e.g. *Ducourant et al. 2014*).

The significant increase in membership statistics does not help to improve our understanding of the origin of ϵ Cha and LCC. Neither does it explain the similarities in their age and kinematics or the apparent separation between them.

Figure 5: The IMF of the ϵ Cha updated census, complete down to $\sim 0.03 M_{\odot}$.

Acknowledgments

K.K., K.M., and V.A.-A. acknowledge funding by the Science and Technology Foundation of Portugal (FCT), grants No. IF/00194/2015, PTDC/FIS-AST/28731/2017, UIDB/00099/2020, and SFRH/BD/143433/2019. We thank Friedrich vom Stein for help preparing this manuscript.